

Higher Order Geometric Sequences: Structure and Formulas

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Abstract

This paper introduces a new mathematical concept, called the Higher Order Geometric Sequence (HOGS), which generalizes the classical geometric sequence to higher orders. A sequence $\{a_n\}$ is defined as a k -th order geometric sequence if its ratio becomes constant after k successive ratio operations. In other words, the number of successive ratio operations required to reach a constant ratio determines the order.

Two equivalent definitions are presented: (1) one based on the number of ratio operations, and (2) another where the exponents of a constant base form a higher-order arithmetic sequence (HOAS). From this structural relationship, it follows that geometric sequences are dependent on arithmetic sequences. This dependence is established analytically through the exponents, which follow an arithmetic structure.

Five fundamental formulas are established, each accompanied by examples and unified proofs. These formulas form the analytical foundation for studying higher order multiplicative structures in discrete mathematics and are applicable to any k -th order geometric sequences.

Keywords: Higher order geometric sequence, Higher order arithmetic sequence, Recurrence relation.

1 Introduction

The classical geometric sequence is defined by the relation

$$a_{n+1} = r a_n \quad (r = \text{constant ratio}),$$

which represents first-order multiplicative regularity.

However, there exist more complex sequences in which the ratio itself changes systematically and becomes constant after multiple ratio operations. Such sequences exhibit higher-order multiplicative regularity, leading to the concept of Higher Order Geometric Sequences (HOGS). The level at which constancy first appears determines the order of the sequence.

The study was motivated, during my early exploration of basic sequence structures in 2021 as a high-school student, by the observation that in a classical arithmetic sequence

the differences between consecutive terms are constant, and in a geometric sequence the ratios between consecutive terms are constant. This naturally leads to the question: what happens if the differences or ratios themselves follow another sequence? In particular, in the context of the present work, what if the ratios of consecutive terms in a geometric progression form another sequence, specifically another geometric progression? This question initiated the investigation of higher-order geometric sequences, where the ratios of consecutive terms themselves form a geometric sequence, and more generally where ratios can follow another well-defined pattern. In earlier explorations, I first examined lower-order cases and identified a pattern that extended to arbitrary order; in this work, I present and prove the resulting general formulas for higher-order geometric sequences.

2 Reference Ratio Table

The ratio structure of a representative third-order geometric sequence is shown in Figure 1. The first diagonal d_1 is highlighted in red, the third diagonal d_3 in blue, and the constant ratio values in bold.

Figure 1: Ratio table of a third-order geometric sequence showing diagonals d_1 (red) and d_3 (blue).

In this figure:

- The first diagonal $d_1 = (1, 2, 3, 5)$,
- The second diagonal $d_2 = (2, 6, 15, 5)$,
- The third diagonal $d_3 = (12, 90, 75, 5)$,
- The constant ratio in the bottom row is 5.

3 Definitions

Definition 1 (Order of a Sequence). *The order of a sequence refers to the minimum number of successive operations required to reach a constant value.*

- For an arithmetic sequence (HOAS), the order is the least positive integer k such that the k -th forward difference is constant [3].

- For a geometric sequence (HOGS), the order is the least positive integer k such that the k -th successive ratio is constant.

Definition 2 (k -th order geometric sequence). A sequence $\{a_n\}$ is defined as a k -th order geometric sequence if its ratio becomes constant after k successive ratio operations. (Equivalently: the successive ratios stabilize at the k -th level.)

Example 1. The sequence 1, 2, 12, 1080, 7290000, ... from the reference table is a 3rd order geometric sequence ($k = 3$), as the constant ratio ($r_k = 5$) is obtained after three successive ratio operations.

Definition 3 (Higher Order Geometric Sequence). A sequence is called a Higher order geometric sequence if it is a k -th order geometric sequence where $k > 1$.

Definition 4 (Diagonal and its properties). In the ratio table, a diagonal is a sequence of $k + 1$ entries that begins in the first row with any term a_d of the original sequence and moves down-right through successive ratio rows until the constant ratio (r_k) in the $(k + 1)$ -th row is reached. For a k -th order geometric sequence:

- Each diagonal contains exactly $k + 1$ entries.
- The diagonal entries are used as base values in the formulas for the n -th term, the product up to the n -th term, and the y -intercept; one may take these base values directly from any chosen diagonal \mathbf{d} .
- The first entry of the chosen diagonal is a term of the original sequence, denoted a_d .
- The last (bottom) entry of that diagonal is the constant ratio for the sequence, denoted r_k .

Definition 5 (Higher Order Arithmetic Sequence (HOAS)). A sequence $\{b_n\}$ is a Higher order arithmetic sequence (where $k > 1$) if its k -th finite differences (Δ_k) are constant and nonzero. Such a sequence can be represented by a degree k polynomial [4].

Definition 6 (Exponent-Based Formulation). For a chosen diagonal, we may write

$$a_n = d^{P(n)},$$

where $P(n)$ is a polynomial of degree k and d is a constant related to the terms of the specific diagonal chosen. This shows directly that the exponents $P(n)$ form a HOAS (degree- k polynomial), so the Higher Order Geometric Sequence is generated through an underlying arithmetic structure.

4 Fundamental Formulas and Examples

Let the sequence be a k -th order geometric sequence. The following five fundamental formulas hold.

- Formulas (1), (2), and (3) are parameterized by a chosen diagonal d with successive diagonal ratios r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k .
- Formulas (4) and (5) depend only on the sequence terms $\{a_n\}$.

4.1 (1) n-th Term

$$a_n = a_d \prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\binom{n-d}{j}}.$$

Example 2. The sequence from the Reference Ratio Table (Figure 1) is 1, 2, 12, 1080, ... ($k = 3$). Determine a_4 .

The first diagonal ($d = 1$) from the Reference Ratio Table (Figure 1) provides the values $a_1 = 1$, $r_1 = 2$, $r_2 = 3$, $r_3 = 5$.

$$a_n = 1 \cdot 2^{\binom{n-1}{1}} \cdot 3^{\binom{n-1}{2}} \cdot 5^{\binom{n-1}{3}}.$$

For $n = 4$: $a_4 = 1 \cdot 2^3 \cdot 3^3 \cdot 5^1 = 1080$.

Using the third diagonal ($d = 3$): $a_3 = 12$, $r_1 = 90$, $r_2 = 75$, $r_3 = 5$.

$$a_n = 12 \cdot 90^{\binom{n-3}{1}} \cdot 75^{\binom{n-3}{2}} \cdot 5^{\binom{n-3}{3}}.$$

For $n = 4$: $a_4 = 12 \cdot 90^1 \cdot 75^0 \cdot 5^0 = 1080$.

Thus, the n -th term can be calculated using any chosen diagonal.

4.2 (2) Product up to the n-th Term

$$P_n = \prod_{t=1}^n a_t = a_d^n \prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\binom{n-d+1}{j+1} - \binom{1-d}{j+1}}.$$

Example 3. The sequence is 1, 2, 12, 1080, ... ($k = 3$). Determine P_4 .

Using the first diagonal ($d = 1$):

$$P_n = 1^n \cdot 2^{\binom{n}{2}} \cdot 3^{\binom{n}{3}} \cdot 5^{\binom{n}{4}}.$$

For $n = 4$: $P_4 = 1^4 \cdot 2^6 \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5^1 = 25920$.

Using the third diagonal ($d = 3$):

$$P_n = 12^n \cdot 90^{\binom{n-2}{2} - \binom{-2}{2}} \cdot 75^{\binom{n-2}{3} - \binom{-2}{3}} \cdot 5^{\binom{n-2}{4} - \binom{-2}{4}}.$$

For $n = 4$: $P_4 = 12^4 \cdot 90^{-2} \cdot 75^4 \cdot 5^{-5} = 25920$.

Thus, the product up to the n -th term can be calculated using any chosen diagonal.

4.3 (3) Y-intercept (value at $n = 0$)

$$a_0 = a_d \prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\binom{-d}{j}}.$$

The value a_0 represents the Y-intercept of the sequence's generating function (the value of the function when $n = 0$). Although this expression includes the diagonal index d , the numerical value of a_0 remains consistent across all diagonal choices.

Example 4. The sequence is $1, 2, 12, 1080, \dots$ ($k = 3$). Determine a_0 .

Using $d = 1$:

$$a_0 = 1 \cdot 2^{\binom{-1}{1}} \cdot 3^{\binom{-1}{2}} \cdot 5^{\binom{-1}{3}} = 1 \cdot 2^{-1} \cdot 3^1 \cdot 5^{-1} = \frac{3}{10}.$$

Using $d = 3$:

$$a_0 = 12 \cdot 90^{\binom{-3}{1}} \cdot 75^{\binom{-3}{2}} \cdot 5^{\binom{-3}{3}} = 12 \cdot 90^{-3} \cdot 75^6 \cdot 5^{-10} = \frac{3}{10}.$$

Hence, the y -intercept remains identical for all diagonals.

4.4 (4) Constant Ratio (r_k)

$$r_k = \prod_{n=s}^{s+k} a_n^{(-1)^{k+s-n} \binom{k}{n-s}}.$$

(The product covers any $k + 1$ consecutive terms starting from index s .)

Example 5. Order $k = 3$. Using the first $k+1 = 4$ terms: $a_1 = 1, a_2 = 2, a_3 = 12, a_4 = 1080$.

$$r_3 = a_1^{-1} a_2^3 a_3^{-3} a_4^1 = 1^{-1} \cdot 2^3 \cdot 12^{-3} \cdot 1080^1 = 5.$$

The same result holds for any consecutive four terms, e.g., $a_3^{-1} a_4^3 a_5^{-3} a_6^1 = 5$.

4.5 (5) Recurrence Relation

$$a_n = \prod_{t=1}^{k+1} a_{n-t}^{(-1)^{t+1} \binom{k+1}{t}}.$$

Example 6. Order $k = 3$. The sequence terms are $a_1 = 1, a_2 = 2, a_3 = 12, a_4 = 1080, \dots$
The recurrence relation is:

$$a_n = a_{n-1}^4 a_{n-2}^{-6} a_{n-3}^4 a_{n-4}^{-1}.$$

For $n = 5$, using the previous $k + 1 = 4$ terms:

$$a_5 = a_4^4 a_3^{-6} a_2^4 a_1^{-1} = 1080^4 \cdot 12^{-6} \cdot 2^4 \cdot 1^{-1} = 7290000.$$

5 Proofs of the Formulas

We begin by establishing the fundamental connection between Higher Order Geometric Sequences (HOGS) and Higher Order Arithmetic Sequences (HOAS).

lemma 1 (Logarithmic Transformation). *If $\{a_n\}$ is a k -th order geometric sequence, then $\{b_n\} = \{\ln a_n\}$ is a k -th order arithmetic sequence.*

Proof. By the Exponent-Based Formulation, let $a_n = d^{P(n)}$, where $P(n)$ is a polynomial of degree k and d is a constant. Taking the natural logarithm:

$$b_n = \ln a_n = \ln(d^{P(n)}) = P(n) \ln d.$$

Since $P(n)$ is a degree k polynomial and $\ln d$ is a constant, b_n is a polynomial of degree k . Therefore, its k -th finite difference (Δ_k) is constant, proving that $\{b_n\} = \{\ln a_n\}$ is a k -th order arithmetic sequence. \square

Diagonal-Based Formulation for HOAS

To derive the HOGS formulas which are parameterized by a chosen diagonal d , we must first generalize the HOAS formula to an arbitrary starting index d .

The standard HOAS n -th term formula is classically formulated using the first diagonal, where $n = d = 1$, as $b_n = b_1 + \sum_{j=1}^k \Delta_j \cdot \binom{n-1}{j}$ [1]. If we start from an arbitrary term b_d (the log-equivalent of a_d), we must account for the $d - 1$ skipped terms. This is achieved by shifting the polynomial basis from $\binom{n-1}{j}$ to $\binom{n-d}{j}$.

Let $\{b_n\}$ be a k -th order arithmetic sequence. The general term of a k -th order arithmetic sequence, based on diagonal \mathbf{d} , is:

$$b_n = b_d + \sum_{j=1}^k \Delta_j \cdot \binom{n-d}{j},$$

where Δ_j denotes the j -th finite difference of the sequence $\{b_n\}$ taken along the chosen diagonal \mathbf{d} (Δ_k is the constant difference).

Proof of Formula (1): n -th Term

Proof. Let $\{a_n\}$ be a k -th order geometric sequence. Then $b_n = \ln a_n$ is a k -th order arithmetic sequence.

Using the diagonal-based HOAS formula with diagonal d :

$$\ln a_n = \ln a_d + \sum_{j=1}^k (\Delta_j) \cdot \binom{n-d}{j}.$$

The j -th finite difference (Δ_j) of the log-sequence $\{b_n\}$ corresponds to the logarithm of the j -th diagonal ratio r_j :

$$\Delta_j = \ln r_j.$$

Substituting this relationship:

$$\ln a_n = \ln a_d + \sum_{j=1}^k \ln r_j \cdot \binom{n-d}{j} = \ln a_d + \ln \left(\prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\binom{n-d}{j}} \right) = \ln \left(a_d \prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\binom{n-d}{j}} \right).$$

Exponentiating both sides yields the formula:

$$a_n = a_d \prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\binom{n-d}{j}}.$$

This proves the n -th term formula for any diagonal \mathbf{d} . □

Proof of Formula (2): Product up to the n-th Term

Proof. We have:

$$P_n = \prod_{t=1}^n a_t = \exp \left(\sum_{t=1}^n \ln a_t \right).$$

Using the n-th term HOAS formula (where $\ln a_t = \ln a_d + \sum_{j=1}^k \ln r_j \cdot \binom{t-d}{j}$):

$$\sum_{t=1}^n \ln a_t = \sum_{t=1}^n \left[\ln a_d + \sum_{j=1}^k \ln r_j \cdot \binom{t-d}{j} \right].$$

Interchanging the order of summation:

$$\sum_{t=1}^n \ln a_t = n \ln a_d + \sum_{j=1}^k \ln r_j \cdot \sum_{t=1}^n \binom{t-d}{j}.$$

Using the binomial summation identity:

$$\sum_{t=1}^n \binom{t-d}{j} = \binom{n-d+1}{j+1} - \binom{1-d}{j+1}.$$

Therefore:

$$\sum_{t=1}^n \ln a_t = n \ln a_d + \sum_{j=1}^k \ln r_j \cdot \left[\binom{n-d+1}{j+1} - \binom{1-d}{j+1} \right].$$

Exponentiating:

$$P_n = a_d^n \prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\left(\binom{n-d+1}{j+1} - \binom{1-d}{j+1} \right)}.$$

This proves the product formula. □

Proof of Formula (3): Y-intercept (a_0)

Proof. Using the n-th term formula (1) with $n = 0$:

$$a_0 = a_d \prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\binom{0-d}{j}}.$$

This gives the y-intercept directly:

$$a_0 = a_d \prod_{j=1}^k r_j^{\binom{-d}{j}}.$$

□

Proof of Formula (4): Constant Ratio (r_k)

Proof. For a k -th order geometric sequence, the constant ratio appears after k ratio operations, which means $\Delta_k \ln a_s = \ln(r_k)$.

The general expression for the constant k -th finite difference is [2]:

$$\Delta_k \ln a_s = \sum_{t=0}^k (-1)^{k-t} \binom{k}{t} \ln a_{s+t} = \ln(r_k).$$

Exponentiating and rearranging:

$$r_k = \exp \left(\sum_{t=0}^k (-1)^{k-t} \binom{k}{t} \ln a_{s+t} \right) = \prod_{t=0}^k a_{s+t}^{(-1)^{k-t} \binom{k}{t}}.$$

Changing index by setting $n = s + t$:

$$r_k = \prod_{n=s}^{s+k} a_n^{(-1)^{k+s-n} \binom{k}{n-s}}.$$

This proves the constant ratio formula. □

Proof of Formula (5): Recurrence Relation

Proof. For a k -th order arithmetic sequence $\{b_n\}$, the $(k+1)$ -th difference is identically zero:

$$\Delta_{k+1} b_{n-(k+1)} = \sum_{t=0}^{k+1} (-1)^t \binom{k+1}{t} b_{n-t} = 0.$$

Substituting $b_n = \ln a_n$:

$$\sum_{t=0}^{k+1} (-1)^t \binom{k+1}{t} \ln a_{n-t} = 0 \quad \implies \quad \ln \left(\prod_{t=0}^{k+1} a_{n-t}^{(-1)^t \binom{k+1}{t}} \right) = 0.$$

Exponentiating and isolating a_n ($t = 0$ term):

$$a_n \cdot \prod_{t=1}^{k+1} a_{n-t}^{(-1)^t \binom{k+1}{t}} = 1 \quad \implies \quad a_n = \prod_{t=1}^{k+1} a_{n-t}^{-(-1)^t \binom{k+1}{t}}.$$

Simplifying the exponent using $-(-1)^t = (-1)^{t+1}$:

$$a_n = \prod_{t=1}^{k+1} a_{n-t}^{(-1)^{t+1} \binom{k+1}{t}}.$$

This proves the recurrence relation. □

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